

Orientalizing infant burials from Gabii, Italy

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Abstract

In recent decades data provided by funerary archaeology has revolutionized our understanding of the proto-urban landscapes of Latium in the early Iron Age. The data that provide a compelling argument for the emergence of fixed systems of social hierarchy contribute greatly to the study of the first wave of urbanism that transformed the Italian peninsula. The discovery in 2009 of two elite infant burials in the Latin city of Gabii contributes to this narrative, as these sub-adults were interred with grave goods that attest to the presence of a system of inherited social rank and thus provide important testimony about Gabii in the Orientalizing period. The funerary data presented here holds the potential of eventually being contextualized alongside settlement data from Gabii.

INTRODUCTION*

The evidence stemming from funerary contexts in Central Italy has, in recent years, substantially influenced the degree to which archaeologists may glean some understanding of the dynamics of the early Iron Age peoples. These cultures typically leave few other material remains in the record but employed funerary practices that preserve traces of information about behavior and society. The discovery in 2009 of two elite infant burials at Gabii in Latium offers an opportunity to discuss two well-preserved funerary assemblages from Iron Age Latium and the current scientific methodologies employed to document such archaeological finds.¹ Additionally, these two newly explored tombs find comparisons in the *necropoleis* of other Latin sites such as Osteria dell’Osa and Ficana, and yet also represent a new chapter in the Sabine funerary record. The ability to precisely document the tombs and their contents *in situ* represents an important application of digital technology to the archaeology of Italy which while not illustrative of a newly invented methodology nevertheless demonstrates afresh the utility and viability of such documentation particularly in the case of fragile funerary contexts.

TOPOGRAPHY OF GABII - ‘AREA A’

The two tombs described in this article were discovered during the course of excavations in July 2009. The excavation campaign of the Gabii Project, under the auspices of the University of Michigan and the Soprintendenza Speciale per i Beni Archeologici di Roma (hereafter SAR) focused on an

approximately 1 ha area of the archaic urban center of Gabii, a primate city-state in Latium, some 18 km east of Rome (fig. 1). During 2007 and 2008 approximately 40 ha of Gabii’s urban area was the subject of a geophysical survey that resulted in the selection of two tracts for excavation.² The northerly tract, located under the administrative umbrella of the SAR, is positioned on the downslope of the extinct volcanic crater of Castiglione, adjacent to other portions of Gabii’s urban center excavated by the SAR and other entities in previous years (fig. 2). The main topographical feature within the excavation area is a side street of the ancient city layout that was identified by survey and that traverses the excavation area from south to north, ascending the downward slope of the volcano crater (fig. 3). To the west of this street, in a sector marked as ‘Area A’, excavation opera-

Fig. 1. Map showing location of Gabii in Central Italy.

Fig. 2. Map showing location of Gabii Project excavation areas.

tions uncovered, at a relatively shallow depth, the tuff bedrock of the volcanic slope into which over 100 anthropic features of varying sizes were cut. The nature of these features varied in terms of size, shape, and preservation. In most cases the combined processes of water infiltration and natural and mechanical erosion had truncated or otherwise destroyed the archaeological deposits that were likely once associated with these features, creating a challenging interpretative situation. While some of the bedrock features are likely associated with a tuff quarry discovered in the northern part of the sector, others were likely funereal in their original usage. In the midst of these truncated features that had been largely stripped of stratigraphic deposits emerged two intact fossa-type tombs, located within an area that surface survey has shown to be densely populated by the end of the 6th century BC.³ These tombs were cut directly into the bedrock surface,

Fig. 3. Aerial photograph of 'Area A'.

Fig. 4. General state plan of 'Area A'.

Fig. 5. Plan of Tomb 10 showing in situ position of grave goods.

SU 338 - d

SU 341

SU 345 - 5

SU 340

SU 347

SU 337 - 2

SU 339 - 1

SU 342 - c

SU 344

SU 343

Fig. 6. Table showing funerary assemblage from Tomb 10.

Fig. 7. Photograph showing bronze ornamentation from Tomb 10.

oriented on a north-south axis. These tombs, herein labeled Tomb 10 and Tomb 11, proved to be the most well preserved archaeological features investigated within Area A during the 2009 campaign (fig. 4). It seems clear, however, that the two tombs discussed here - both of which date from the first half of the 1st millennium BC - likely predate many of the other surrounding bedrock features and that their preservation can be attributed to a deep original cutting that subsequently afforded protection from later disturbances and intrusions, including plowing. The following report shall present a summary of the contents of each tomb and will also discuss the methodological approach to documentation employed in the field as well as the implications of these infant tombs for the archaeology of early Latium.

TOMB 10

Tomb 10 is a north-south oriented *fossa* tomb (SU 181) cut into the tuff bedrock and was excavated and studied at the end of July 2009. The tomb cut measures approximately 1.05 m long and 0.26 m deep (fig. 5). Sheer sides characterize the *fossa*, as does a relatively level floor upon which the de-

ceased and the accompanying grave goods were deposited. On the basis of the anthropological evidence, the deceased was placed in a supine position and while the skeletal remains are extremely degraded, the preliminary data suggests an individual of 1.5 to 2 years of age, determined on the basis of dentition.⁴

An elaborate funerary assemblage accompanied the deceased, composed of 10 ceramic vessels and eight pieces of bronze ornamentation (figs 6, 7). The ceramic elements of the funerary assemblage, for the most part, were positioned at the feet of the deceased while the bronzes decorated the torso and upper body; two vessels, in fact, were positioned so as to frame the head of the inhumant. The ceramic assemblage consists of high quality vessels in *impasto* fabric that, with the exception of an over-painted Geometric skyphos, all have burnished surfaces.

TOMB 11

Tomb 11 was discovered in close proximity to other anthropic features cut into the bedrock. This tomb is composed of an oblong, rectilinear fossa with the addition of a rock-cut *loculus* along the eastern side of the tomb (fig 8).⁵ The tomb measures roughly 1.05 m long and 0.25 m deep, although its plan is not completely regular. Post-depositional intervention caused serious distur-

Fig. 8. Plan of Tomb 11 showing in situ position of grave goods.

Fig. 9. Table showing ceramic funerary assemblage from Tomb 11.

Fig. 10. Photograph of impasto askos from Tomb 11 (SU 177-1).

bance to the remains of the individual buried in the tomb; a preliminary examination of the bones shows evidence of what is likely post-depositional animal turbation. This is most evident in the form of two punctures caused by the teeth of a small carnivore visible on the fragmentary remains of the left tibia.⁶ In terms of the physical limit of the *fossa*, a later circular cutting in the bedrock surface

interrupted the southwest corner of the tomb, but this event does not seem to have disturbed the tomb's contents in any measurable way.

The assemblage of grave goods consisted of seven ceramic vessels and one bead (fig. 9). The grave goods had been positioned carefully in the tomb with three vessels positioned around the inhumant (T. 11, nos 1 through 3) and the other four (T. 11, nos 4 through 8) placed in the stone-cut *loculus* along the eastern side of the tomb. The *loculus* assembly comprised two Etrusco-Corinthian vessels and two *impasto* vessels, including an askos with stamped designs (fig. 10). The *loculus* was further protected by the placement of two stones that served to effectively close off the opening.

Documentation

In the case of both tombs, the delicate nature of the archaeological context required quick attention during the excavation process but at the same time demanded careful and exact documentation. Traditional excavation methodology recommends that tombs, like most archaeological features, be drawn by the triangulation method

Fig. 11. Geo-referenced orthorectified photographs are used to digitize the finds from the infant burials. From the top down: Geo-referenced orthorectified photograph, Digitization of the finds from the photograph, Final vector data in the site GIS.

in order to record the position of any human remains as well as any artifacts within the context of the tomb. The fieldwork at Gabii instead employs a different approach to the documentation of such features, namely photogrammetry. While this technique has been in use in recent years, it does not enjoy wide application in Italy. The use of photogrammetric documentation at Gabii represents a new phase in the application of this technique within the context of urban archaeology in Italy. Advances in digital recording technology allow for a more rapid and more accurate recording process that produces not only first rate documentary data, but also can produce three-dimensional digital reconstructions of archaeological contexts.

Field Methodology

Photogrammetry in archaeological documentation is certainly not a new development, although it has been recently overlooked due to the increased utilization of more expensive means such as laser scanners. New developments in software and digital photography, however, have made photogrammetry a much more efficient and cost-effective choice, while at the same time delivering similar results as more expensive and time consuming techniques.

The Gabii Project uses photogrammetry, and the PhotoModeler Scanner software specifically,⁷ to document complex or important finds and surfaces for two primary purposes.⁸ The first is the creation of orthorectified, geo-referenced photographs used for digitization of finds and contextualization of drawings (fig. 11). The use of geo-referenced photographs for digitization of layers is not a new one, but Photomodeler software dramatically cuts down the amount of time needed in the field. Photographs can be taken at any angle and orthorectified through the software, making the use of quad-pods or other leveling devices unnecessary. For complex assemblages, such as burials, the time needed to traditionally document each find would completely halt the excavation for an extended period of time. In burials where materials are in danger of degradation and under threat of looting, long periods of exposure can be extremely detrimental. By using this methodology, however, we are able to precisely determine the three-dimensional location of objects and to plan from the orthorectified photograph. Since the model is tied within the local coordinate system, it can be integrated into the site GIS, allowing for its contextualization in three-dimensions with other finds and surfaces throughout the site.

The second purpose is to generate point meshes of the surface to convey its topography and to build a three-dimensional model.⁹ The PhotoModeler Scanner extension allows for the creation of dense surface meshes with points at a specified interval (the majority of our projects use a 2 mm spacing) (fig. 12). This produces results that are similar to a terrestrial laser scanner, but at a fraction of the cost (only the digital camera and the software itself) and set-up time. The detailed three-dimensional models that are then produced assist in the visualization of archaeological features and create a type of documentation that is much more realistic and complete than either traditional plans drawn by hand or two-dimensional photography.

INFANT BURIALS IN LATIUM

Infant burials in Iron Age Latium are well attested archaeologically and the visibility of these tombs makes a clear statement about the role of infant burials in Latin society.¹⁰ The visibility of these tombs in the record also attests to the high rate of infant mortality in the ancient Mediterranean world.¹¹ The study of this class of tombs has intensified in recent years in light of major excavations like those at Osteria dell'Osa, Ficana, Satricum, and the Palatine Hill in Rome.¹²

In Rome the phenomenon of infant burials is well attested in the archaeological record. Einar Gjerstad excavated numerous infant and child tombs in the late 1940s and 1950s, and, like Giacomo Boni before him, concentrated on the Iron Age necropolis adjacent to the Temple of Antoninus and Faustina.¹³ Gjerstad also excavated tombs on the Palatine Hill itself, including the rich tomb of a child beneath the Aula Regia that dates to the second half of the 7th century BC (Latial IVB) and was presumed to be associated with a hut. This rich tomb included one imported aryballos (ca 640-625 BC) as well as two 'imitation' aryballoi (IVB).¹⁴ At Ficana (Monte Cugno) along the *via Ostiense*, a total of 21 infant and child tombs were excavated, with some being a *fossa* and others a *vaso* (*enchytrismos*) burials.¹⁵ The funerary custom at Ficana is analogous to the evidence uncovered by Gjerstad in Rome. In chronological terms, the Ficana burials are concentrated in the Latial IIIB-C and Latial IVA periods. The archaeological evidence from numerous other Latin sites, including Castel di Decima, Acqua Acetosa Laurentina, Satricum, Ardea, and Lavinium - Pratica di Mare, show that the custom of infant and child burial is widespread in Latium and we should note that this distinctly Latin habit differs from the contemporary

Fig. 12. Three-dimensional model from PhotoModeler Scanner. Clockwise from top left: Point mesh of surface at 2 mm spacing, Surface created from point mesh, Closer view of point mesh.

customs of Etruria where sub-adult burials are often not spatially discrete from adult funerary populations.¹⁶ It is worthwhile to note that Pliny the Elder discussed the phenomenon of infant burials that took place within or very near to the context of the Roman house.¹⁷ These tombs, known as *subgrundaria* (literally meaning 'beneath the eaves'), existed already in the early Iron Age as the infant depositions investigated by Gjerstad and others in and around the *Sepolcretum* in Rome are located in proximity to the foundations of Iron Age huts. The placement of the burials may also serve to delimit, in a spatial sense, the boundaries of the household, marking them as distinct from an adjoining boundary or the neighboring house.

Pliny goes on to remark that infant burials were treated as inhumations since it was not the custom (*mos gentium*) to cremate individuals before they cut their first teeth.¹⁸ The liminal status of infants even affected the grieving process, as recorded by authors including Plutarch who laments the untimely death of the 'newly born' but also feels these deaths are borne more easily than others¹⁹ and that a ritual prohibition attributed to Numa prevented mourning for anyone less than three years of age.²⁰

The phenomenon of archaeologically visible infant and child burials with grave goods in Latium is one whose incipit is to be connected

with the Latial III period (ca 770-730 BC). In the Latial II phase, there are generally no elaborate assemblages; when they are present, they tend to be simple, with the most common ceramic form being the two-handled, footed vase and deep cups with biforal handles (forms 10 and 22). Additionally, the presence of used, and often broken, vessels characterize early Latial II child tombs.²¹ From the Latial III period onwards, infant and child tombs are often found within or in close association with houses, but it is not known if this behavior continues the behavior of earlier periods (i.e. Latial I and Latial II).²²

Chronology of the Gabii Tombs

The chronology of the two tombs described above is of course a key issue and the ability to contextualize these tombs benefits enormously from the vast and reasonably well-published scholarship connected with this cultural phenomenon. The funerary assemblage of Tomb 10 allows it to be dated to the Latial IIIB to Latial IVA1 phases (second half of the 8th to the beginning of the 7th centuries BC). As the comparisons above suggest, the grave goods find numerous close parallels with artifacts known from Osteria dell'Osa as well as other Latin sites, including new sites that continue to be uncovered. It is also important to note the close analogy, in terms of comparable artifacts, that can be made between the Gabine tombs and the tombs collected and published by Gierow from the area of Latium in proximity to Lake Nemi and Lake Albano. The high quality *impasto* vessels, along with the bronze ornamentation, attest to the elite nature of the burial. The grave goods find close comparison with the infant tombs from the Via Sacra necropolis in Rome and with those from the minor acropolis of Lavinium-Pratica di Mare.²³ Additionally, the adornment of the inhumant with the bronze pendants and bosses underscores the important place of ritual and apotropaic devices in Iron Age funerary customs.²⁴

Tomb 11, on the other hand, is more recent than Tomb 10. Here the overall date of the grave assemblage relates to the Latial phases IVA2 to IVb, or the middle of the Orientalizing period (mid 7th to early 6th centuries BC). Of particular note within the funerary assemblage is the *impasto* askos (fig. 10). While other askoi are present in the literature relevant to Iron Age tombs in Latium, this particular form is not well attested. Its form differs noticeably from the other ceramic vessels in this assemblage, contrasting starkly with the painted Etrusco-Corinthian wares made of a light fabric.

This askos may well reproduce an ancient form originating in the Final Bronze Age and extending into the Latial I period.²⁵ This would seem to indicate that the askos is a particularly important vessel and that its placement in the tomb may have held a special ritual significance, perhaps analogous to the placement of the apotropaic *bul-lae* in Tomb 10.

CONCLUSIONS

The Gabii tombs, taken together with the other archaeological evidence pertaining to infant burial in 1st millennium BC Latium, underscore the importance of this funerary custom and indicate that the Latin people attached a special social significance to the burial of elite infants. Pliny the Elder's discussion reflects the lasting significance of this special funerary practice and suggests that in the Iron Age funerary record, infants enjoy a special status. While hundreds of tombs are known archaeologically from the environs and immediate outskirts of Gabii (viz. Osteria dell'Osa), the discovery of Geometric and Orientalizing burials within the urban center itself represents a new archaeological horizon, one that offers a potentially unique circumstance to contextualize sub-adult burials in a new way, effectively examining and documenting these contexts that encapsulate important evidence about the processes of urbanism in central Italy.

CATALOG OF TOMB CONTENTS

Tomb 10 assemblage

1. Globular two-handled *impasto* vessel (SU 337-2)

Description: This *impasto* vessel has two cuspidate handles extending from the shoulder to the rim, each with three projections. The body is burnished and an *umbilicus* is present on the belly. The base is flat and the rim is plain. A series of vertical impressions decorate the belly and flank the attachment points of the handles. *Measurements:* Height 10.3 cm; height with handle 13.9 cm; base diameter 4 cm; rim diameter 6.9 cm; handle diameter 1.0-1.3 cm.

Comparanda: OdOt. 558.1 (fig. 3c.62); OdO t. 552.7 (fig. 3c.64); OdO t. 264.4 (fig. 3b.46); OdO t. 148.2 (fig. 3c.25); OdO t. 63 (fig. 3c.27).

2. Brown *impasto* carinated cup (SU 338-d)

Description: The vessel has a flat base, cylindrical neck, a plain rim and a high, vertical, biforal handle extending from the rim to the shoulder. A finger-marked, pinched design decorates the carination.

Measurements: Height 6 cm; height with handle 10.7 cm; base diameter 3.5 cm; rim diameter 8.7 cm; handle diameter 0.8 cm.

Comparanda: OdO t. 204.4 (fig. 3c.33); OdO t. 301(M7).4; OdO t. 120.5; Odo t. 120.8; OdO t. 552(M3).8; Lucrezia Romana, II, 2003, tomb 2 [SAR inv. 518129] (Tomei 2006, 368 II.650).

3. Globular two-handled *impasto* vessel (SU 339)

Description: This two-handled vessel, now missing one of the handles, has an umbilicus on the belly. The surface has been burnished but is otherwise devoid of decoration.

Measurements: height 6.8 cm; base diameter 2.9 cm; rim diameter 4.9 cm; handle width 1.0-1.3 cm.

Comparanda: OdO t. 252.1 (fig. 3b.26); t. 253.2 (fig. 3b.37).

4. Miniaturistic painted *impasto* skyphos (SU 340)

Description: This vessel is an over-painted, miniaturistic *impasto* skyphos. The piece was found entirely intact. The vessel has a slightly concave base, deep convex body with rounded shoulders, and the body from the shoulder to the rim is roughly vertical but curving slightly inward while the rim curves slightly outward. Two ring handles at the shoulder point obliquely outward and upward. A painted geometric design covers the skyphos and can be divided into three registers. The bottom third of the piece is covered by solid red paint. On the shoulder between the handles there is a series of six vertical lines separated by five horizontal lines that encircle the entire vessel. The upper third between the shoulder and the rim is filled with alternating horizontal lines encircling the vessel. The handles are painted.

Measurements: Height 5.6 cm; base diameter 2.8 cm; rim diameter 7.6 cm; handle diameter 0.9 cm.

Comparanda: OdO t.109.8 (fig. 3a.37); t. 392.7 (fig. 3a.301); OdO t. 562.5 (fig. 3c.46); Gierow 1964 fig. 89.5, 89.6; Gierow 1964 fig. 88.9; Ficana t.13.3 (nos 96-99).

5. Lug-handled *impasto* cup (SU 341)

Description: This *impasto* cup, with a single lug handle has a flat base and an inward curving rim. A crimped geometric pattern is present on the handle and a segmented geometric design on shoulder that is composed on groupings of three vertical lines.

Measurements: height 5.2 cm; base diameter 4 cm; rim diameter 13 cm; handle diameter 1 cm.

Comparanda: OdO t. 7.1 (fig. 3a.412); t. 33.5 (fig. 3a.425); t. 414.6.

6. *Impasto* cup (SU 342-c)

Description: This plain *impasto* cup has a dark fabric and a single high, vertical biforal handle. The vessel has a plain rim and a flat base.

Measurements: Height 4.7 cm; height w/ handle 8.7 cm; base diameter 2.4 cm; rim diameter 6.3 cm; handle diameter 0.7 cm.

Comparanda: -

7. Two-handled cuspidate *impasto* vessel (SU 343)

Description: This vessel has a flat base and the lower part of its body is funnel-shaped. An *umbilicus* is present and two vertical band handles extend from the shoulder to rim, each with three pointed projections.

Measurements: Height 8.4 cm; base diameter 4 cm; rim

diameter 12 cm; handle diameter 1.2 cm.

Comparanda: OdO t. 551.6; OdO t. 552.7; OdO t. 558 (M6).1; OdO t. 194.2; OdO t. 228.2.

8. Two-handled carinated basin (SU 344)

Description: This *impasto* basin has a flat base and two handles that originate at the shoulder and flare obliquely outward and upward. The carinated vessel is decorated with a finger-marked, pinched design along the carination. The rim flares outward.

Measurements: Height 7.3 cm; base diameter 6.1 cm; rim diameter 23.2 cm; handle diameter 1.3 cm.

Comparanda: Cf. Marina, Riserva del Truglio no 9 (Gierow 1964, 221 no 9); Marino, Prato della Corte no 11 (Gierow 1964, 255 fig. 151); Colle della Noce t. 2 (Ardea 1983 fig. 56)

9. Amphora (SU 345-5)

Description: Two-handled buccheroid *impasto* amphora with two simple band handles extending from shoulder to rim. The surface has been burnished and an impressed arcuated design decorates the body.

Measurements: Height 7.8 cm; base diameter 3.2 cm; rim diameter 5.7 cm; handle width/diameter 0.5 cm.

Comparanda: OdO t. 178.3 (fig. 3c.7).

10. Carinated *impasto* patera (SU 347)

Description: This burnished patera has a burnished body and a rim that flares outward from the carination. The base is flat and the belly has a funnel-shaped profile. The vessel has two parallel holes to facilitate hanging.

Measurements: Height 2.9 cm; base diameter 4.2 cm; rim diameter 11.4 cm.

Comparanda: Cf. OdO 434.4 (fig. 3c.19) with a higher foot profile.

11. Lunate bronze *bulla* (SU 349)

Description: This bronze *bulla* was originally placed on the torso of the deceased along with no 12 and nos 14-17 below, and likely was connected to no 13 below. This *bulla* is fashioned from sheet bronze that has been folded over and fastened along the lower edge with wire; circular ringlets at the outer corners allowed for attachment to the chain. The surface of the bronze is, in this case, unadorned.

Measurements: Width approx. 12 cm; height approx. 6 cm.

Comparanda: Palatine Hill, north slope, tomb 1, area VII, sector 5 [US 12988] SAR inv. 519120, 519124, 519125. Latial IIIB2 (Tomei 2006, 75); Narce Tomb 23M (UPenn MS 1044; Turfa 2005, 106 no 38); Marino, Riserva del Truglio, t. 29 no 33 (Gierow 1964, 211); Marino, Riserva del Truglio, t. 12 no 10 (Gierow 1964, 167); see also the example from Satricum (Gnade 2007, 107 no 32).

12. Lunate bronze *bulla* with repoussé design (SU 349)

Description: Deposited in a manner overlapping no 11 above, this *bulla* is morphologically similar but has an elaborate surface decoration in the form of a geometric pattern executed in the repoussé technique. This pattern consists of rows of bosses that alternate with tool lines composed of pinpoints.

Measurements: Width approx. 12 cm; height approx. 6 cm.

Comparanda: Narce Tomb 23M (UPenn MS 1044; Turfa 2005, 106 no 38).

13. Bronze link chain for pendants (SU 346)

Description: This bronze chain was originally attached to the pectoral pendant (no 11 above), and perhaps to others of the bronze pieces as well. About 25 links of the chain survive, with another two links still attached to the upper edge of pendant no.

Measurements: Length approx. 15 cm.

Comparanda: Linked chains abound in tombs. See, e.g., Narce Tomb 23M (UPenn MS 1069A; Turfa 2005, 104 no 35).

14. Bronze boss (*borchia*) (SU 349)

Description: A worked, geometric boss made from sheet bronze.

Measurements: Diameter approx. 1.5 cm.

Comparanda: Narce Tomb 43 (late 8th century BC) (UPenn MS 865; Turfa 2005, 116 no 55).

15. Bronze boss (*borchia*) (SU 349)

Description: A worked, geometric boss made from sheet bronze.

Measurements: Diameter approx. 1.5 cm.

Comparanda: -

16. Bronze boss (*borchia*) (SU 349)

Description: A worked, geometric boss made from sheet bronze.

Measurements: Diameter approx. 1.5 cm.

Comparanda: -

17. Bronze boss (*borchia*) (SU 349)

Description: A worked, geometric boss made from sheet bronze.

Measurements: Diameter approx. 1.5 cm.

Comparanda: -

18. Bronze fibula bow (SU 349)

Description: A plain, undecorated bronze fibula. Semi-circular. Pin, loop, and catch-holder are missing.

Measurements: Diameter approx. 5 cm.

Comparanda: -

Tomb 11 assemblage

1. Bead (SU 172)

Description: A small bead, pierced at the center, made from vitreous paste.

Measurements: Height 0.4 cm; width 0.6 cm.

Comparanda: OdO t. 82 (fig. 3c.13).

2. Etrusco-Corinthian bowl (SU 174-6)

Description: This open bowl has a ring foot and a flat base and a flaring rim. The light fabric is decorated by alternating linear bands. The rim has two holes pierced through the thickness in order that the vessel might be hung or suspended from a hook or cord. Wheel-made.

Measurements: Height 4 cm; base diameter 3.5 cm; rim diameter 12.3 cm.

Comparanda: OdO t. 192.1 (fig. 3c.77); OdO t. 54.1 (fig. 3c.78); OdO t. 326.9 (fig. 3b.16); OdO t. 269.2 (Gruppo N, Tomba 269; fig. 3b.34); Crustumerium, località Sasso Bianco, t. 34 (Tomei 2006, 225 II.198); OdO t. 270.3 (fig. 3b.43); OdO 274.9 (fig. 3c.84).

3. Piriform aryballos (SU 175-4)

Description: This piriform aryballos was preserved intact. It has a ring foot and a concave base. Its banded, geometric paint scheme extends from foot to shoulder and includes a painted trace on the rim. There is one strap handle extending from the shoulder to the rim.

Measurements: Base diameter 1.7 cm; height 10.3 cm; rim diameter 4 cm; diameter of handle 0.5 cm.

Comparanda: Lucrezia Romana, II, 2004 t. 7 (SAR inv. 514495) (Tomei 2006, 371 II.670); Palatine Hill, Aula Regia tomb (Colonna 1978 tav. XVI B); Ficana t. 2.1, t. 2.2 (Brandt 1997, 133 figg. 66, 67).

4. Miniaturistic buccheroid *impasto* olpe (SU 176-3)

Description: This burnished miniaturizing vessel was discovered intact and upright in the northern part of the tomb. The olpe has a ring foot with a flat base, a conical body with a carinated rounded shoulder, conical neck with an out-flaring rim, and a vertical biforal handle extending from the rim to the shoulder.

Measurements: Height 7 cm; height with handle 9.5 cm; base diameter 2.8 cm; rim diameter 5 cm; handle diameter 0.3 cm.

Comparanda: Odo t.163.2 (fig. 3a.42); OdO t. 62 Bachina Nord 8 (Tav. III A 8 p. 201); OdO t. 62 (Tav. LV 24 p. 203); Gierow 1964 (fig. 86.7); Gierow 1964 (53.9); Marino t. 23 Gierow II 112.8; Ficana t. 2.5 (66 67e)

5. *Impasto* cup with single handle (SU 177a-2)

Description: An *impasto* cup with a single, plain handle; the cup has a flat base, high, vertical slides with a rim that flares outward slightly.

Measurements: Height 5.2 cm; height with handle 8.2 cm; base diameter 4.3 cm; rim diameter 7.9 cm; handle diameter 0.8-1.1 cm.

Comparanda: OdO t. 56.4bis (fig. 3c.81); OdO t. 552.8 (fig. 3c.64).

6. Etrusco-Corinthian vessel (SU 177-5)

Description: This is a closed vessel form whose fabric and decoration is quite similar to no 7 below. The vessel has a ring foot and a flat base. Its light fabric is decorated with a linear pattern composed of alternating bands with a wavy band on the shoulder. The neck flares out to join the broad, flat rim that is painted a dark color on its upper surface. Wheel-made.

Measurements: Height 9.7 cm; base diameter 4.1 cm; rim diameter 9 cm.

Comparanda: Decorative scheme comparable with numerous Etrusco-Corinthian vessels, e.g. vessels from Lucrezia Romana II, 200, Tomb 7 (Tomei 2006, 371).

7. Etrusco-Corinthian *olla* (SU 177-1)

Description: This is a closed vessel form with a ring foot and flat base. The belly flares outward and tapers toward the neck and the broad, flat rim. The light fabric of the vessel carries a painted design that has been applied rather unevenly, but consists of alternating linear bands with a wavy band on the shoulder. Wheel-made.

Measurements: height 7 cm; base diameter 3.4 cm; foot height 3.2 cm; rim diameter 6.3 cm.

Comparanda: Decorative scheme comparable with numerous Etrusco-Corinthian vessels, e.g. vessels from Lucrezia

Romana II, 200, Tomb 7 (Tomei 2006, 371). cf. Marino, Riserva del Truglio, t. 23 no 2 (Gierow 1964, 189) and Marino, Riserva del Truglio, t. 21 nos 5, 7 (Gierow 1964, 186).

8. *Impasto* askos (SU 177-1)

Description: This vessel was among those placed in the tomb's loculus. This *impasto* askos has a flat base and a flaring mouth, with a single lug handle. The decorative scheme stands out in this assemblage, as a series of three stamped impressions decorate each shoulder. The vessel has been burnished.

Measurements: Height 8.6 cm; base diameter 4 cm; rim diameter 3.2 cm.

Comparanda: Pascolano tomb 1, no 8 (Gierow 1964 fig. 134); Mario, Vigna Delsette (Gierow 1964 fig. 157); Marino, San Rocco, Capo d'Acqua (Latial II) (Gierow 1964 fig. 164); Rocca di Papa, San Lorenzo Vecchio, tomb O, no 8 (Gierow 1964 fig. 169); Castel Gandolfo, San Sebastiano - mixed find groups of Latial II period (Gierow 1964 fig. 181 no 34); Castel Gandolfo (Gierow 1964 fig. 194, no 23; fig. 203, no 51 and 52; fig. 206, no 26).

NOTES

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¹ Becker/Mogetta/Terrenato 2009, 629-642.

² Guaitoli 1981.

³ A. Nava 2009. Internal report, Soprintendenza per i Beni Archeologici di Roma.

⁴ Similar to OdO t. 362.

⁵ Horwitz/Smith 1988, 471-481; Dominguez-Rodrigo/Piqueras 2003, 1385-1391.

⁶ Eos Systems Inc. 1992-2009 PhotoModeler Scanner.

⁷ See Rabinowitz et al. 2008 for where this particular method of photogrammetry was derived as well as a more detailed description of the procedure.

⁸ For both of these end products, however, the same method is used in the field. The only difference is the amount of processing time needed for each product.

⁹ The phenomenon of sub-adult burials also holds particular relevance for Italo-Roman ritual connected with the stages of maturity, as reviewed and discussed in Dasen 2009. In Latin contexts we should be careful to differentiate between the burials of infants and children. For the people of ancient Italy, the *infans* was a not-yet-speaking individual.

¹⁰ Hopkins 1983, 255 estimates that 28% of Roman babies who were born alive died by their first birthday. Also, Dasen 2009, 210-11.

¹¹ De Santis et al. 2007-2008 provides an up-to-date summary and statistical discussion.

¹² Gjerstad 1956: tomba H (88), Tomba EE (102-103), Tomba MM (110-111), Tomba FF (144-145), Tomba D (117-120), Tomba G (120-124).

¹³ Ampolo 1978, 122-125.

¹⁴ Brandt 1997; Fischer-Hansen 1997.

¹⁵ Bartoloni 2003.

¹⁶ Plin. *HN* 7.15. Fulgentius *Expositio sermonum antiquorum* 7 also remarks on these *subgrundaria* as the place of burial for children less than 40 days old ('*quid sint subgrundaria*').

¹⁷ Plin. *HN* 7.72. '*Hominem prius quam genito dente cremari mos gentium non est.*'

¹⁸ Plut. *Moralia* 113D; other authors represent slightly divergent viewpoints, viz. Horace *Epistles* 1.7.2ff.

¹⁹ Plutarch *Numa* 12.2.

²⁰ See Bietti Sestieri 1992: Osteria dell'Osa, t. 559 and t. 586. T. 541 shows miniaturizing vessels.

²¹ See OdO t. 122 and t. 109.

²² Castagnoli 1972.

²³ Waarsenburg 1995.

²⁴ A.M. Bietti Sestieri. Personal communication. December 2009.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Ampolo, C. 1978, Tomba infantile, sotto il palazzo dei Flavi - tav. XVI, B, in G. Colonna (ed.), *Civiltà del Lazio Primitivo. Palazzo delle Esposizioni, Roma, 1976*, Rome, 122-125.

Bartoloni, G. 2003, *Le società dell'Italia primitiva: lo studio delle necropoli e la nascita delle aristocrazie*, Rome.

Becker, J.A./M. Mogetta/N. Terrenato 2009, A new plan for an ancient Italian city: Gabii Revealed, *AJA* 113.4, 629-642.

Bietti Sestieri, A.M. 1992, *La necropoli laziale di Osteria dell'Osa*. 3 v. Rome.

Brandt, J.R. 1997, *Scavi di Ficana 2. Il periodo protostorico e arcaico*, Rome.

Castagnoli, F. 1972-1975, *Lavinium*, Rome.

Crescenzi, L. 1983, *Ardea: immagini di una ricerca; Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale "Vittorio Emanuele II"*, giugno 1983, Rome.

Dasen, V. 2009, Roman birth rites of passage revisited, *JRA* 22, 199-214.

De Santis, A./M. Fenelli/L. Salvadei. 2007-2008, Implicazioni culturali e sociali dal trattamento funebre dei bambini nella protostoria Laziale, in G. Bartoloni (ed.) *Sepolti tra i vivi / Buried among the living: evidenza ed interpretazione di contesti funerari in abitato (Scienza dell'antichità 14/2)*, Rome, 725-741.

Dominguez-Rodrigo, M./A. Piqueras. 2003, The use of tooth pits to identify carnivore taxa in tooth-marked archaeofaunas and their relevance to reconstruct hominid carcass processing behaviours, *Journal of Archaeological Science* 30, 1385-1391.

- Fischer-Hansen, T. 1990, *Scavi di Ficana 1. Topografia generale*, Rome.
- Gierow, P.G. 1964, *The Iron Age culture of Latium II.1: excavations and finds: the Alban Hills*, Lund.
- Gjerstad, E. 1956, *Early Rome II: the tombs*. Lund.
- Gnade, M. (ed.) 2007, *Satricum. Trenta anni di scavi olandesi (catalogo di mostra a Le Ferriere 2007-2008)*.
- Guaitoli, M. 1981, Gabii. Osservazioni sulle fasi di sviluppo dell'abitato, in *Ricognizione archeologica. Nuove ricerche nel Lazio*, Florence, 23-57.
- Hopkins, K. 1983, *Death and Renewal*, Cambridge.
- Horwitz, L.K./P. Smith. 1988, The effects of striped Hyaena activity on human remains, *Journal of Archaeological Science* 15, 471-481.
- Rabinowitz, A./L. Sedikova/J. Trelogan/ S. Eve 2008, New methodologies at an ancient site: digital technology and excavation in the Southern Region of Crimean Chersonesos, 2001-2006 (=Novi metodologii doslidzhennya pam'yatki davnini: tzifrovi tehnologii ta rozkopki u Pivdennomu rajoni Chersonesa Tavrijs'kovo), *Archeologia* 2008 (1), 71-81, and 2008 (2), 69-78.
- Turfa, J.M. 2005, *Catalogue of the Etruscan gallery of the University of Pennsylvania Museum of Archaeology and Anthropology*, Philadelphia.
- Waarsenburg, D. 1995, *The northwest necropolis of Satricum. An Iron Age cemetery in Latium Vetus*, Amsterdam.

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